

Chatbots- Strategy for Boosting Customer Experience to the Next Level

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Abstract

Companies have fundamentally shifted towards customer centric approach in decision making. They got an access to customer data. Companies are realizing impact of good or bad customer experience on retention. Customers with positive experiences are more likely to continue purchases, customers with bad experience either stop spending or decrease their spending. Communicating with the customers at the right time and right way is quiet challenging. An efficient use of machine learning and intelligence can give an opportunity to build memorable interaction with audience and build rapport.

In response to increased expectations, chatbots are cost effective solutions to bridge the gap between rising customer expectations and a company's current level of service. Chatbot offers a range of benefits that takes the customer experience to next level.

The Research Paper has been prepared with the following objectives:

- *To study the importance of improving customer experience*
- *To incorporate Chatbot into marketing strategy to drive improvement in customer experience*
- *To understand the Challenges in implementing Chat bots and measure to overcome it*

Data has been collected from various secondary sources like journals, companywide surveys etc to analyse the issues relating to customer experiences and challenges in integrating personalized interactions through chatbots.

Keywords: Customer Experience, Trends, Chatbot, Challenges in implementation

Introduction

It was assumed that success of business were quality product, best customer service, value for money etc. But with the advent of social media and real time interactive feedback, the customers are building relationships and expecting fulfillment of promises from company. Today's consumers have large number of choices than ever before and are pursuing it through various channels. People demand experiences that are actually relevant for them and being forced to ingest stuff that is irrelevant will not bring pleasant experience. If the business doesn't save their

customers time, make their life easier and better, there will be risk of disruption by someone who can offer.

Literature review

Customer experience is an outcome of interaction between an organization and a customer over a period of relationship. The customer interaction consists of his journey, brand touch points, and the environment during their experience. If the expectations meet during his journey from all contact points, the experience considered to be good one. Customers respond both to direct and indirect contacts. Direct contact may be as a result of direct purchase or usage by the consumer. Indirect contact results from exposure to advertising, reviews, criticism, and news reports etc. The experiences undergone by customers are unique and personal. It may be memorable or not depends upon the stimulations created before, during and after purchase on sensory, emotional, physical aspects of a person. Companies by controlling the stimuli can control the reaction of the consumer. Customer may interact through web, social media or over the phone customer service or face to face interaction as in retail service.

Kotler et al. 2013, (p. 283) say that customer experience is about, “Adding value for customers buying products and services through customer participation and connection, by managing all aspects of the encounter”. The encounter includes touchpoints. Businesses can create and modify touchpoints so that they are suited to their consumer which changes/enhances the customers’ experience.

Methodology

The study is descriptive research based on secondary data, which was collected from Internet and other secondary sources like published surveys, books, magazine, newspaper, published journal etc.

Statement of Problem

Customers of today demand hyper-personalisation of everything. It is possible when the company leverages a deep understanding of customer preference, customer data, and conversations across channels and able to anticipate a customer’s needs

Scope of the study

Study takes into account Customers interaction in traditional platform and digital platform. It is assumed that companies and customers are ready to adopt new technologies.

Objectives

- To study the importance of improving customer experience
- To incorporate Chatbot into marketing strategy to drive improvement in customer experience
- To understand the Challenges in implementing Chat bots and measure to overcome it

Trends in Customer Journey with Company

Following are the developments taking place in customer’s interaction with the company product and services. Companies are taking measure to retain the customers.

- Customers hate waiting, often we could see them waiting over phone while employees figure things out or looking through information to solve queries.
- Company used to rely on employee’s judgment that looks through the data to identify how to best serve the customer. Instead leveraging predictive and self-learning analytics to find customers at risk of churn and proactively offer personalised offers.

- Companies are focusing on customer experience cloud which is leveraging customer data, digital experience and personalization to manage interactions with customer.
- Customers want to have personalized interaction with brand to build relationship or to solve problems.
- Augmented reality can give customers more realistic idea of an expected experience or helps customer to make better decision for themselves and their family.
- Primary goal of the business is to keep customers happy, there is a need to equip employees with right tools and training to be able to use technology to achieve it

Chatbot

In few cases, a person is better than a machine. But when processing a large amount of data in real time relating to customer, a machine is simply better at it. Front desk employees can process too little, too late. With the use of artificial intelligence can identify opportunities and experiences relevant for the customer

Chatbots are computer generated programs that use artificial intelligence to initiate and carry on conversations with consumers, to meet their needs, to answer frequently asked questions and to provide customer support after a sale. It can reduce customer wait times and can provide customers with 24/7 service even when customer service representatives are not there to answer incoming queries. Chatbots can be used to engage customers with outbound marketing activities like announce new product, routine follow up messages to ensure customer satisfaction, wishing people on special occasion and offering discount offer to drive sales etc. In the event of issue raised by customer, chatbots can be programmed to send directly to concerned person to resolve issues.

Chatbot in marketing strategy

Marketing strategy is a game plan for reaching people and turning them into customers of the product or service. AI technology aids the business in attracting and retaining the customers. Chat bots are one of the machine learning tool enables the business to meet customer expectations. Chatbots other than improving customer service they educate and inform customers. It can deliver mass information at an individual level by integrating with social media, gather data about single person with whom they interact. When user poses an inquiry, it can answer it accurately by offering personalised shopping advice based on purchase history and preferences. It shows larger engagement capacity through proactive approach. By sending automatically welcome notification to customers visiting webpage or social media, it builds interactions with the user. The automation eliminates need for human agents for routine questions and requests. So employees will get more time to focus on those tasks that require human attention. By naturally posing questions in conversations while collecting feedback, the risk of incomplete questionnaire in survey can be reduced to some extent. With right machine learning tools, it can analyse feedback and information it gathers from users and gives insight into what audience exactly wants. Later marketing strategy can be remodelled to focus on customer needs. The various survey analysis shows consumers not interested in emails, text messages and other notifications every time so chatbots capacity to capture, analyse data helps in sending relevant, personalised notification to each and every user. The capacity to make interaction fun by adding humour element creates lasting impression on the user. It can increase the number of visitors by sharing links to blogs, gifs, emojis that is by improving content. Lead nurturing is very essential in generating new customers for the business. Data generated by Chatbots helps gathering information and generating personalized messages thereby marketing efforts can be channelized towards each and every lead.

Challenges in implementation

- Making Affordable Chatbots – Specialist are required to create tailor made to business model and to generate expected end-user interactions.
- Making secure chatbots – As its collects all the personal data of the user throughout the journey of interactions, if security not provided users refuse to use the chatbot.
- User behaviour is controlled by emotions. Feelings are not permanent and mood changes with triggers. Challenge is understanding user expression in messages.
- Users demand for more or best experience, People want to use chatbots that are smart and at par level with human.
- User has limited attention span and often distracted. The challenge is how to hook them and respond in a manner to grab user’s attention.

Measures to popularise Chatbots in business

- Chatbot should provide real value to users. It should make lives of the user easy by responding appropriately to the request by identifying as regular or of particular importance.
- Tech devices suffer from tag called ‘gimmick’. Ensure people like chatbots by delivering good quality and relevant responses by not becoming over friendly device.
- Provide effective small talk experience as customers or users annoyed of wasting time on unwanted interactions.
- Incorporate methods to review the conversation transcripts, assess their success and make alteration if required to language scripts or functions.
- Ensure user has always access to chatbot conversations as human tendency to close accidentally or bury the window. To overcome this risk embeds the chat window at appropriate place in gadgets.
- In order to reach to their highest potential, chatbots need to be programmed to a level of emotional level in order to understand the problem.

Conclusion

At the outset, by implementing chatbots into marketing strategy it’s possible to learn about audience, tailor marketing efforts and reach new customers. While there are technical challenges to be met in specifying script and functions for an enhanced interactions. Based on survey results and expert opinion, assumption can be drawn that chatbots has a capacity to replicate actual human conversation and can be coded to have more intelligent responses to customer queries. It cannot replace completely meaningful human interaction with customer but provide way for engaging with customers, information and suggestions for improving core product and services.

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